

Chalkones. Part V. Synthesis of Hydroxy- and Methoxy-Chalkones and their Derivatives

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Syntheses of some new hydroxy- and methoxy-chalkones by the Claisen-Schmidt condensation have been effected. The functional derivatives of some of the chalkones have been prepared.

In continuation of the previous work on chalkones (Dhar and Lal, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 1159; Dhar, *ibid.*, 1960, **25**, 1247, this *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 320, 363, 496, 799; *J. Sci. Res., Agru Univ.*, 1961, **10**), the present communication reports the synthesis of some hydroxy- and methoxy-chalkones and their derivatives, viz., acetyl, benzyloxy, and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chalkones were prepared as described by Schraufstatter and Deutsch (*Ber.*, 1948, **81**, 489). The acetyl, benzyloxy, and 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives were prepared according to the standard procedures.

TABLE I

Chalkone.	Colour & cryst. shape.	Cryst. from.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
2,3-Dimethoxy-2'-hydroxy-	Yellow needles	Ethanol	99-100°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₄	C: 71.7% H: 5.4	71.8% 5.6
2,2'-Dihydroxy-3-methoxy-	,,	,,	151-52°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄	C: 71.0 H: 5.2	71.1 5.2
2'-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-	Stellate aggregate of yellow needles	,,	91-92°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃	C: 75.4 H: 5.6	75.6 5.5
2',3-Dihydroxy-	Golden yellow prismatic needles	Aqueous ethanol	161°	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃	C: 75.1 H: 4.9	75.0 5.0

TABLE II

Chalkone (derivative).	Colour & cryst. Shape.	Cryst. form.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
2-Acetoxy-2',3,4'-trimethoxy-	Pale yellow, elongated prisms & hexagonal plates	95% Ethanol	90-91°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₆	C: 66.7 H: 5.5	67.4 5.6
2-Acetoxy-2',4',6'-trimethoxy-	Dull apple-green crystals	Ethanol	88-89°	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₆	C: 67.4 H: 5.4	67.4 5.6
3-Methoxy-2,2',4'-triacetoxy-	Pale yellow prisms	Ether-pet. ether	93-94°	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₈	C: 64.0 H: 4.8	64.1 4.8
2',4',3-Triacetoxy-	Pale yellow biconvex plates	Ethanol	99-100°	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₇	C: 66.2 H: 4.7	65.9 4.7
3,4'-Dibenzoyloxy-2'-hydroxy-	Yellow microneedles	Benzene-ethanol	134-35°	C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₄	C: 79.8 H: 5.4	79.8 5.5

2-Benzoyloxy-2',3,4'-trimethoxychalkone separated as a yellow oil, which failed to crystallise.

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TABLE III

Chalkone 2,4-D.N.P.	Colour and crystalline shape.	Cryst. from.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found.	Calc.
2,3-Dimethoxy- 2'-hydroxy-	Red microneedles	Ethanol	220-21°	$C_{23}H_{20}O_7N_4$	11.9	12.1
2,2'-Dihydroxy- 3-methoxy-	"	"	237-38°	$C_{22}H_{18}O_7N_4$	12.8	12.4
2'-Hydroxy- 4-methoxy-	Orange, hair-like needles	Xylene	254°	$C_{22}H_{18}O_6N_4$	12.8	12.9
2-Hydroxy- 2',3,4'-trimethoxy-	Bright red, rod-like microcrystals	Ethyl acetate	222°	$C_{24}H_{22}O_8N_4$	11.4	11.3
2-Benzoyloxy- 2',3,4'-trimethoxy-	Deep orange-red needles	"	193-94°	$C_{31}H_{28}O_8N_4$	9.8	9.6
2-Hydroxy- 2',4',6'-trimethoxy-	Vermilion rod- type microneedles	Ethanol- acetone	220-21°	$C_{24}H_{22}O_8N_4$	11.5	11.3
3-Methoxy- 2,2',4'-trihydroxy-	Deep red microneedles	Ethyl acetate	207-208°	$C_{22}H_{18}O_8N_4$	11.9	12.0
2',3-Dihydroxy-	Bright red microneedles	" "	233-35°	$C_{21}H_{16}O_6N_4$	13.0	13.3
2',3,4'-Trihydroxy-	Orange, slender microneedles	Ethanol	224-25°	$C_{21}H_{16}O_7N_4$	12.5	12.8

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